

CONSTRUCTION ON MARS

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Abstract

Terraforming Mars is a crucial endeavor due to pressing issues on Earth, including resource depletion. As our planet's resources dwindle, Mars offers a potential solution through colonization and construction. Terraforming involves altering Mars' environment to make it habitable for humans and other organisms. Key steps include creating a thicker atmosphere to retain heat, generating a stable climate, and introducing liquid water by melting polar ice caps. These changes could support plant growth and potentially sustain a human population. However, terraforming Mars is an immense challenge. Mars has a thin atmosphere with minimal greenhouse gases, making it cold and inhospitable. Additionally, building habitats, establishing infrastructure, and ensuring sustainability demand advanced technologies and significant resources. While the idea of colonizing Mars offers hope for humanity's future, it's crucial to approach this endeavor thoughtfully and ethically. As we explore this path, we must weigh the benefits against the challenges and carefully consider our responsibilities as both planetary stewards and pioneers. In this article, we have a look at the issues that are needed to build a house on Mars and we will analyze it in general.

Keywords: building, Mars planet, terraforming, construction, future

Introduction

The fourth planet from the sun is Mars. It merely has a diameter that is half that of the earth. However, the earth exhibits a variety of traits, and these traits make us think that life may also exist on Mars. These astronauts discovered that Mars is a frigid, arid planet that resembles the Moon more than the Earth. The Martian atmosphere has an exceedingly low density, about 50 km above sea level, comparable to the Earth's atmosphere (1). A modest amount of water and carbon dioxide make up the majority of this atmosphere. Nitrogen and oxygen have not been identified in it, though they certainly exist in minuscule amounts. The air on Mars is so thin that UV radiation, which is harmful to the majority of living organisms, can easily travel there from space. The polar caps are made of frozen water, and a sizable portion of Mars' surface was once covered in water. More than the other planets, Mars has captured the interest of scientists. This is due to two key factors. Mars is the planet that is closest to Earth among those that are farthest from the Sun. One of the brightest celestial objects in our night sky, Mars occasionally passes within a relatively short orbital range of the Earth, which is 56 million kilometres away. This planet is orange-red in appearance and is clearly visible to the unaided eye. There are numerous similarities between Mars and Earth. A Martian day is only a little over 40 minutes shorter than ours. An atmosphere exists on Mars. It has seasons and an ice cover on its poles, just like the earth. Many scientists formerly thought that there could be a garden on our planet. Since then, other unmanned spacecraft have visited Mars, and reports and photographs have returned to Earth (2). These texts almost provide us with proof that there is no life on this planet, but perhaps Mars' former climate was more conducive to life. Unfortunately, the Martian atmosphere, which primarily contains carbon dioxide and a trace quantity of water vapour, is not breathable for humans. Intense interest in Mars exploration and the potential for future Martian migration has been generated by these characteristics of Mars and its distinctive geography and landforms. Future Mars exploration missions will continue to make progress with the aim of better understanding Mars' internal structure and external environment, as well as laying the groundwork for the eventual realisation of a human mission to the planet. As a result, Mars buildings are crucial for the administration of building information. mostly because these researchers are only starting out (3,4). Figure 1 shows the contrasts between the two Sierras.

Figure 1. Comparison of the planet Earth and Mars (Esa, 2018)

Methodology

This article attempts to provide thorough information regarding the future of construction on Mars based on prior studies and a review of the literature. The resources available on Mars will be used for this purpose to study and investigate the facilities and goods required for development projects on this planet.

study area

The best chance that a planet has the necessary quantity of water to host life is Mars. However, from both an engineering and an economic perspective, the most crucial question is whether it is feasible to live there. As was already said, Mars is the planet closest to Earth, but there is one major difference: there is no oxygen-rich atmosphere on Mars. As a result, the main duties involve warming and thickening the atmosphere there. The initial colonists had to construct an underground shelter in order to comprehend this truth (5). Figure 2.

Figure 2. A settlement on Mars (Robert Lea. 2023)

For the Martians, building shelters is crucial because of the planet's low air pressure, intense solar radiation, and requirement for colonies that can last without pressure suits. The first colonists and planetary engineers should reside in their spacecraft and in habitation modules that have been transported from Earth. Structures must be built using the materials at hand because there are no cement manufacturers or forests to harvest on Mars. On Mars, there are plenty of rocks and dirt; similar building materials have been employed for thousands of years on Earth. Caves, stone that has been stacked and mortared, adobe, and rammed earth are all examples of this type of construction. Cast stabilized earth, earth-bag buildings, and dug subsurface rooms are more recent examples (6).

Buildings formation

Building structures on Mars presents unique challenges and opportunities due to the planet's harsh environment and distinct characteristics. The buildings intended for Mars colonization must be designed to

provide essential life support, protect against extreme temperatures, and support the well-being of human inhabitants (7). The architecture of Martian buildings would likely incorporate modular and self-sustaining designs. To counteract the thin atmosphere and high levels of radiation, structures could be partially buried or constructed with thick walls using Martian regolith as a building material. This would provide natural insulation and protection against radiation, as well as stabilize temperatures within the living spaces. These buildings might consist of interconnected modules, each serving specific functions such as living quarters, research areas, and food production zones (8). Figure 3 shows building Formation on Mars.

Figure 3. building formation on mars (Anthony Cuthbertson, 2021)

Challenges of Construction on Mars:

As Ehlmann, et al (9) note, the prospective benefits Martian exploration overrides the costs. It had been investigated and reported that in a long term perspective, even the expense analysis rationalizes the Martian exploration when it is compared to the other governmental expenditures. The Several technological aspects are present for colonization of Mars. Issues such as low gravity, low atmospheric pressure, temperature variation throughout a day, etc. The list even goes down to the most human’s basic needs namely food, water, oxygen, shelter, and clothing. Solutions had been scientifically studied to overcome these barriers. To name a few in accordance with Elhmann (9). evaluation the technological advancement mentioned in table 1 can be seen as an approach towards these problems:

Table 1 Facing challenges and solutions in Mars mission (Gharizadeh at el, 2019)

Challenge to a human Mars mission	Technology development	Technology development
The negative effect of microgravity and solar radiations on human	Pharmacological and mechanical prevention techniques	Prevention, detection, and treatment of illnesses ranging from osteoporosis
Limited air, water, and food resources	Closed loop life-support systems	Conservation, waste management and recycling

Limited energy supply	Solar energy, low energy uses, graphene panels	Renewable efficient energy sources; energy
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Innovative Construction Techniques (3D Printer)

3D printing, or additive manufacturing, constitutes a revolutionary suite of technologies that facilitate the creation of three-dimensional objects by layering material to form a complete product. The core principle involves translating a digital design into a tangible object through a sequential layering process. This versatility spans from crafting elementary items like chess pieces to fabricating intricate components like rocket engine parts. In the realm of construction, 3D printing follows a similar *modus operandi* but operates on a grander scale (12). This method involves employing a 3D printer to deposit layers of various materials to build structures layer by layer. Notably, this technique's efficacy is not restricted to traditional construction materials alone; it extends to an array of substances including concrete, cement, mortar, plastics, mud, rice waste, sand, and even metals and stones. Recent research is heralding a profound development in this field by proposing that Mars' indigenous soil itself holds the potential to serve as a feasible medium for 3D printing structures (13). This discovery bears significant implications for prospective human habitation on the Red Planet. By harnessing Martian soil as a raw material, future settlers and explorers could potentially utilize 3D printing technology to construct habitable shelters, research stations, and other essential infrastructure. This could dramatically streamline the complexities associated with transporting construction materials from Earth, thereby reducing cost, risk, and logistical challenges (14). The form of the settlement's building via 3D printer is shown below.

Figure 4. construction of the settlement by 3D printer (Madeleine, 2022)

Materials and Resources

The biggest problem regarding materials for colonists is the fact that there are none available on the Mars (15). In order to successfully create a sustainable and safe colony for future humans, one must bring either the materials, the technology, or both from Earth for developing and creating long-term housing units for the lunar and Martian astronauts (16). While the composition of the moon and Mars are different than the Earth in some ways, they also share some similarities. Most importantly the natural regolith, or rocky soils, of these planetoids can potentially be used to create the necessary building materials for housing and other buildings and structures (17). There are also plentiful mineral resources including iron, titanium, nickel,

aluminum, sulfur, chlorine and calcium. Silicon dioxide is the most common material on Mars, according to measurements taken by the Viking space probes, and is also a basic ingredient of glass (18).

Materials That Can Be Used to Construct on Mars

Flexibility, strength, and durability have been the fundamental concerns of professionals while exploring materials to construct on mars. Potential sub-materials that could be used to build buildings on Mars include:

Martian Soil: Martian soil was defined as a weakly consolidated weathered material mainly composed of regolith, aeolian, or fluvial deposits. It also includes a subtle mixture of mineral sediments, ores of dust, and soil. Researchers believe that martian soil can be used as an aggregate for construction (19,21). When supported by engineering and mechanics, the particles theoretically showcased an incredible ability to bond with each other. This implies that when compressed together, they could be used to form building blocks and serve as an alternative for bricks (20,22). Figure 5 depicts a sample of Martin soil.

Figure 5. a sample of martin soil (Baillot, 2017)

Basalt: In the event of a volcanic eruption, the solid rocky remains of the lava, on cooling down turn into igneous rock. These rocks are extensively available throughout mars, with the chemical richness of magnesium and iron. These clusters of rock are mainly categorized based on their availability and the elements that they bind with (23). Some types include lime-ash basalt, which is rich in high silica glass, pyroxene basalt, which contains olivine, and lime-ash basalt which constitutes olivine and lime-ash. The most advantageous property of using basalt for construction is its ability to act as an in-situ resource for 3D printing. Also when heated and extruded, it produces stone wool, which could be used for thermal insulation and protection of surfaced buildings. It could also be used for the construction of cobblestones and decorative crafts (24). Figure 6 depicts a sample of basalt.

Figure 6. a sample of basalt (augite basalt, 2019)

Volcanic Ash: Another residual of a volcanic eruption is the molten magma which breaks down into smaller particles to form volcanic ash. This element, when combined with lime, creates hydrates of the elements and bonds with them to showcase hydraulic gelling abilities, which can be used in combination with cement, either as an admixture for concrete or simply as a binding material to help bind the structure together. With the availability of extensive amounts of iron-containing volcanic ash, throughout the surface of mars, it becomes an essential element that could potentially be used for future constructions on the planet (25). Figure 7 depicts a volcano on Mars.

Figure 7. volcano on mars (Esa, 2010)

Martian Concrete: Concrete primarily requires three elements for its production. The first is an aggregate, for which as discussed earlier, an ample amount of Martian soil could be used. The next is water, which can be found on the polar caps of the planet, in the form of ice. And the last is a binder that uses a combination of sulfur or other polymers with regolith to sustain high-strength bonds under varying atmospheric pressures and temperatures. Similarly, magnesium-based geopolymers could also be used (26). Figure 6 depicts a piece of Martian concrete.

Figure 8. a sample of Martian concrete (Bob Yirka, 2016)

Habitat Design and Functionality

Habitat design and functionality on Mars necessitate innovative solutions due to the planet's harsh environment and unique challenges. Mars has a thin atmosphere, extreme temperatures, and high levels of radiation, which demand specialized habitats to ensure the safety and well-being of human occupants (27). Designing habitats for Mars involves several key considerations. First, the structure must provide effective shielding against radiation and insulation against temperature fluctuations. Materials with high radiation resistance and insulating properties are crucial. Additionally, the habitat should be airtight to maintain a breathable atmosphere, possibly relying on advanced life support systems to recycle air and manage waste. Functionality is paramount to support human life and activities (28). Habitats need to incorporate advanced life support technologies to produce food, water, and oxygen. Closed-loop ecosystems that recycle resources can minimize dependence on Earth supplies. Furthermore, integrating renewable energy sources like solar panels is essential to power habitats and reduce reliance on limited local resources. Flexibility and expandability are also important. Habitats should be designed to accommodate growth as the Mars settlement evolves (29). This could involve modular construction, allowing for the addition of new sections or modules as needed. Additionally, the habitat layout should consider psychological well-being, incorporating communal spaces, natural lighting simulation, and greenery to counteract potential feelings of isolation and confinement (30). Figure 9 depicts an example of a hypothetical design on Mars.

Figure 9. simulated design on Mars (Tyler Koslow, 2015)

Development line:

Future research directions in the realm of Mars construction offer exciting opportunities for scientific investigation and innovation. One line of inquiry could be to look into new technology designed for Martian construction. Researchers can investigate the development and implementation of advanced 3D printing techniques, robotics, and automation systems, which will be required for the construction of habitats, infrastructure, and other structures on Mars. Examining the particular technical hurdles connected with Martian architecture is another intriguing field of inquiry. Researchers can look into topics including adapting construction methods to Mars' harsh environment, dealing with limited resources like water and energy, and developing effective waste management and recycling systems in a closed-loop ecosystem. Furthermore, investigating innovative materials appropriate for Martian construction is an important research field. Scientists can explore locally derived minerals on Mars, such as regolith and ice, to design building materials that are both sustainable and resistant to the planet's severe circumstances. Investigating the characteristics and technical potential of these materials, as well as testing their durability under Martian conditions, could be part of the research. At the end, future research in Martian construction could take numerous paths, including breakthroughs in construction technology, answers to technical obstacles, and the production of novel Martian building materials. Researchers can pave the road for long-term and successful human exploration and colonization of Mars by addressing these issues, making it a more habitable and feasible destination for future missions.

Conclusion:

Construction on Mars signifies an awe-inspiring leap in human capabilities, embodying the relentless pursuit of progress and the human spirit's indomitable nature. Through a synergistic fusion of spacefaring expertise and cutting-edge engineering, the prospects of establishing a viable settlement on the red planet are steadily maturing. By harnessing local resources, like Martian regolith and ice, and leveraging 3D

printing and autonomous construction, we're poised to erect habitats and infrastructure that can withstand the planet's harsh conditions. This venture symbolizes humanity's audacity to expand its horizons, prompting collaboration among diverse fields and international partners. Lessons from terrestrial sustainable practices must be ingeniously adapted, addressing challenges like radiation exposure and life support systems. The evolving narrative of Mars construction narrates not just a technological saga, but also a testament to human adaptability, resilience, and unity in the face of the unknown.

Reference

1. National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Available from Internet: <<http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/>>.
2. Wazman. Lots of People Have Theories About Neil Armstrong's 'One Small Step for Man' Quote, Here's What We Really Know, 2019, Online available from <https://time.com/5621999/neil-armstrong-quote/>
3. A. Todhunter, M. Crowley, and F. Sartipi, "Construction productivity indices in socialism compared with capitalism," *Journal of Construction Materials*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.36756/JCM.v1.1.2>.
4. [2] A. Todhunter, M. Crowley, M. Gholamisheverini, and F. Sartipi, "Advanced technological implementation of construction and demolition waste recycling," *Journal of Construction Materials*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.36756/JCM.v1.1.3>.
5. The Green Geek. Terraforming Mars – part 2. Available from Internet: <<http://www.greengeek.ca/terraforming-mars-part-2/>>.

6. NASA Quest: Possibility of colonizing Mars. Available from Internet: <http://quest.nasa.gov/mars/ask/colony/Colonization_of_Mars_by_humans.txt>.
7. [k/colony/Colonization_of_Mars_by_humans.txt](http://quest.nasa.gov/mars/ask/colony/Colonization_of_Mars_by_humans.txt)>. 4. The Green Geek. Terraforming Mars – part 4. Available from Internet.
8. Mars Ice House: Tour a Concept Martian Home in Pictures, 2018, Online available from <https://www.space.com/39761-mars-ice-house-concept-in-pictures.html>.
9. B. L. Ehlmann et al., "Humans to Mars: A feasibility and cost–benefit analysis," *Acta astronautica*, vol. 56, no. 9-12, pp. 851-858, 2005.
10. M. Gamil, A. Gharizadeh, and F. Sartipi, "A review on graphene reinforced cement composite: technical approach for ecofriendly construction," *Journal of Construction Materials*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.36756/JCM.v1.1.4>. Institute of Construction Materials.
11. F. Sartipi, A. Gharizadeh, and M. Gamil, "Electrical resistance of graphene reinforced cement paste," *Journal of Construction Materials*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2019, doi:
12. Bak, D. (2008). Rapid prototyping or rapid production? 3D printing processes move industry towards the latter. *Assembly Automation Rapid Prototyping Journal Iss Rapid Prototyping Journal*, 23(1), 340–345. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1108/01445150310501190>
13. Mueller, S., Mohr, T., Guenther, K., Frohnhofen, J., & Baudisch, P. (2014). faBrickation: Fast 3D Printing of Functional Objects by Integrating Construction Kit Building Blocks. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/2556288.2557005>
14. Tibbits, S. (2014). 4D printing: Multi-material shape change. *Architectural Design*, 84(1), 116– 121. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ad.1710>
15. R. Garner. How to Protect Astronauts from Space Radiation on Mars, NASA, 2015, Online available from <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/goddard/real-martians-how-to-protect-astronauts-from-space-radiation-on-mars>.
16. N. Savage. To build settlements on Mars, we'll need materials chemistry, 2017, Online available from <https://cen.acs.org/content/cen/articles/96/i1/build-settlements-Mars-ll-need.html>.
17. M. Iranfar, and S. S. Muhy Al-Din. The Cognition of the Architectural Styles Role on Thermal Performance in Houses of Semi-Arid Climates: Analysis of Building Envelope Materials, *Civil Engineering and Architecture*, Vol. 8, No. 5, pp. 929 - 941, 2020, DOI:10.13189/cea.2020.080520
18. Materials Scientists Make Martian Concrete, MIT Technology Review, 2016, Online available from <https://www.technologyreview.com/s/545216/materials-scientists-make-martian-concrete/>.
19. J. Bell et al., "Mineralogic and compositional properties of Martian soil and dust: Results from Mars Pathfinder," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, vol. 105, no. E1, pp. 1721- 1755, 2000.
20. M. Fateri, A. Gebhardt, and M. Khosravi, "Experimental investigation of selective laser melting of lunar regolith for in-situ applications," in *International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition (ASME)*, 2013, vol. 2.
21. G. Jordan. Can Plants Grow with Mars Soil, NASA, 2015, Online available from <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/can-plants-grow-with-mars-soil>.
22. B. Granath. Lunar, Martian Greenhouses Designed to Mimic Those on Earth, NASA, 2017, Online available from <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/lunar-martian-greenhouses-designed-to-mimic-those-on-earth>.
23. Kemmerer, B.W. (2019), A Compositional Analysis of Artificial and Terrestrial Analog Martian Regolith Simulants. Dissertation, Space Sciences: Astronomy/Astrophysics Florida Institute of Technology.

24. Sumanarathna, A.R. (2020), An Introduction to Geology Of Mars. South Asian Astrobiology & Earth Science Research Unit: Eco Astronomy Sri Lanka, Presentation, May 2020 DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11022.38720
25. Touns, L., Hoffman, S. and Watts, K. (2016). Mars Surface Systems Common Capabilities and Challenges for Human Missions. [ebook] Available at: <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/archive/nasa/casi.ntrs.nasa.gov/20160001039.pdf> [Accessed 1 Nov. 2017].
26. E.W. Clifton, Design and construction for a permanent presence on Mars, The Case for Mars V, Mar 26 – Mar 29 1993, Univelt Inc, Boulder, CO, United states, 2000, pp. 451-458.
27. T. Sinn, and O. Doule. Inflatable structures for Mars Base 10, 42nd International Conference on Environmental Systems, 1-12, 2012.
28. T. Talbert. NASA Seeks Ideas for Where on Mars the Next Giant Leap Will Take Place, NASA, 2015, Online available from <https://www.nasa.gov/journeytomars/mars-exploration-zones>
29. E. Mahoney. Where on Mars Might Humans First Land, NASA, 2015, Online available from <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/where-on-mars-might-humans-first-land>.
30. S. Häuplik-Meusburger, and O. Bannova. Space Architecture Education for Engineers and Architects, Space.
31. https://www.esa.int/ESA_Multimedia/Images/2018/04/Comparing_the_atmospheres_of_Mars_and_Earth
32. <https://www.space.com/mars-settlements-people-personalities-number>
33. <https://www.independent.co.uk/space/elon-musk-mars-city-wealth-b1784062.html>
34. <https://www.3dnatives.com/en/using-3d-printing-to-conquer-outer-space-210420226/>
35. <https://www.science.org/content/article/bricks-made-martian-soil-may-be-stronger-steel-reinforced-concrete>
36. <https://fineart.ha.com/itm/meteorites/martian/nwa-8159-martian-meteoritemartian-augite-basalt-moroccofound-2013/a/5438-72121.s>
37. https://www.esa.int/Science_Exploration/Space_Science/Mars_Express/Volcanic_ash_in_Meridiani_Planum
38. <https://phys.org/news/2016-01-martian-concrete-materials-red-planet.html>
39. <https://3dprintingindustry.com/news/3d-printing-a-habitat-made-of-mars-earth-the-sfero-concept-57449/>
- 40.